

**COMPUTER AIDED MATERIALS IN TEACHING MATHEMATICS FOR
GRADE SIX PUPILS OF QUITERIO SAN JOSE ELEMENTARY
SCHOOL, DISTRICT OF TERESA**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 29

Issue 9

Pages: 1384-1389

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2819

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14569035

Manuscript Accepted: 12-02-2024

Computer Aided Materials in Teaching Mathematics for Grade Six Pupils of Quiterio San Jose Elementary School, District of Teresa

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Abstract

The study examined the perceptions of the pupils on the effectiveness of computer aided materials in teaching mathematics with respect to their study habits, class participation and problem-solving skills. Data were drawn from all 258 grade six pupils of Quiterio San Jose Elementary School during the school year 2014 – 2015. The study was conducted using descriptive survey research design. Based on the findings, the effectiveness of computer aided materials in teaching mathematics with respect to study habits, class participation and problem solving is perceived to be much effective. The perceptions of male and female respondents were found to be significantly different with respect to class participation. Another significant difference was found on the effectiveness of the computer aided instruction to their study habits when grouped by monthly family income. The study concluded that there is no significant difference on the perception of the respondents on the effectiveness of computer aided materials in teaching Mathematics with respect to study habits, class participation and problem solving in terms of their age, monthly family income and parents' educational attainment. This study recommends the use of computer aided instructions in teaching pupils mathematics. Personnel with expertise in pedagogy and computer programming are needed to benefit from computer aided instruction. Availability of such number of computers and adequate software is possible in the near future. Implement the proposed program to enhance the attitude toward mathematics and performance in Mathematics in the study as approved by the school authorities. Allocate enough funds for the implementation of the program. Future researchers should undertake researches to determine the effectiveness of various types of computer aided materials.

Keywords: *computer-aided materials, mathematics, elementary*

Introduction

Technology has become a common place in our everyday life. Almost all transactions nowadays keep current with the technological advancements. Technological hardwares and softwares are rapidly changing and upgrading and young generations seem to find it a must to be updated and have a hold of it. It has actually become a necessity to have of one these gadgets like cell phone, laptop, computer or other technological device. It has actually become a tool of communication, relating, living and even learning. Technology is everywhere and it is inevitable because it is part of progress and development.

There is technology in all fields including the educational arena and it is called educational technology. Part of this technology is how to make use of the modern tools and approaches for more effective teaching and learning. Instructional materials must be abreast of the modern technology.

This implies that there is a need for the teachers to develop instructional materials to make the teaching and learning process more meaningful, interesting, relevant and consequentially improve the performance of the learner. Since it has been the clamor of every institution to facilitate quality learning, thus keeping abreast and utilizing the different devices and modern technology to maximize the efficiency and effectiveness of instruction is necessary. An area that benefits with the use of technological advancement is in understanding mathematics. Historically, mathematics has often been considered a subject understood by only a selected and talented few. At the same time, the negative attitude in the subject decreases the level of performance of the students when using the traditional way such like worksheets, drill board, counters, board work etc. which make the pupils bored.

The use of technology and computer software in the classroom allows the pupils to discover and solve more real-world based problem situations, and beside this it also allows for extra time to be devoted to the development of higher order cognitive abilities, such as problem solving and conceptual understanding. It is believed that what is needed in a school mathematics curriculum is to take advantage of computer technology to assist pupils in becoming powerful and thoughtful "problem solvers." Moreover, it is hoped that computers can offer a connection between hands-on experiences and abstract learning. In parallel with the technological advances; technological, particularly computers began to be used in educational environments to develop audio visual materials such as animation and simulation, which resulted in the development of the computer-based instruction techniques.

Being the grade coordinator in the field of Information and Communication Technology and a Mathematics teacher as well, the researcher observes that most of the teachers are still using traditional way in teaching mathematics making use of lecturing, assignments, board work and work sheets while some teachers make use of computer aided materials in teaching Mathematics using the Active Inspire in the E-classroom. It is also observed that pupils using the computer aided materials are more active in the teaching and learning activities become enjoyable and they learn willingly, by playing and enjoying during these activities. Because children of today are very fond of using technologies it is easy for them to manipulate computers, tablets and other gadgets creating an exciting

and interesting game-like atmosphere. Furthermore, computer-based teaching serves to create interest and a learning centered-atmosphere, and helps increase the pupils' motivation that provides them with a more suitable environment to learn.

The main objective of teaching mathematics with the use of Information and Communication Technology in all schools in the District of Teresa is to promote greater achievement and understanding of the subject. It should be based from the pedagogical foundations of humanistic philosophy to provide the pupils successful and enjoyable experiences, in a rich and supportive mathematical environment. It enhances the contribution to learning outcomes through integration of Information and Communication Technology to gain in-depth knowledge and understanding to enhance competencies in Mathematics.

Since every school is a recipient of the E-learning package, teachers of Teresa are encouraged to use the E-classroom at least once a week for the pupils to be more experienced and prepared for the 21st century learning and further enhance their skills in Mathematics using computer aided materials. Most of the teachers in the district have their own computer aided materials inside their rooms to be used in the different learning areas. This opted the researcher to conduct a study related to Information and Communication Technology (ICT). For this reason, the study was conceived to determine the effectiveness of the use of computer aided materials in teaching Mathematics for grade six pupils.

Research Questions

The main purpose of the study was to assess the effectiveness of computer aided materials in teaching Mathematics for grade six pupils in Quiterio San Jose Elementary School Year 2014-2015. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following problems:

1. What is the profile of the grade six pupils' respondents in terms of?
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. monthly family income; and
 - 1.4. parents' educational attainment?
2. What is the level of effectiveness of computer aided materials in teaching Mathematics as perceived by pupil-respondents with respect to:
 - 2.1. study habits;
 - 2.2. class performance; and
 - 2.3. problem solving skills?
3. Is there a significant difference on the perception of the respondents on the effectiveness of computer aided materials in teaching Mathematics with respect to the cited aspects in terms of their profile?

Literature Review

Gadanidis and Geiger, (2010) cited that technological tool include those that are both content specific and content neutral. In Mathematics education, content-specific technologies include computer algebra systems; dynamic geometry environments; interactive applets; handheld computation, data collection, and analysis devices; and computer-based applications. These technologies support students in exploring and identifying mathematical concepts and relationships.

In addition, Arnold (2010) cited that Computer-Aided Instruction (CAI) is a diverse and rapidly expanding spectrum of computer technologies that assist the teaching and learning process. Examples of CAI applications include guided drill and practice exercises, computer visualization of complex objects, and computer-facilitated communication between students and teachers. Computer-Aided Instruction can dramatically increase a student's access to information. The program can adapt to the abilities and preferences of the individual student and increase the amount of personalized instruction a student receives.

Relatively, as cited in the article of PRNewswire, (2010), as schools struggle to increase Math achievement and improve science, technology, engineering and Mathematics (STEM) education, research shows computer-aided instruction (CAI) is a proven, cost-effective solution to the nationwide problem. In addition, a new white paper published by the International Center for Leadership in Education (ICLE) titled The Effectiveness of Computer-Aided Mathematics Instruction in the New Era of STEM Education concludes CAI has been proven to work at scale in independent scientifically based research studies and can help schools address the many challenges of STEM education. Computer aided instruction offers advantages over traditional instruction, including one-on-one interaction, multimedia capabilities that enrich the lesson presentations, self-pacing and instantaneous feedback.

Likewise, Inan (2012) cited that Computer Aided Instruction is an instruction material presented with the use of a computer. Computer Aided Instructions either present information or fill a tutorial role and testing the student for comprehension. By providing one-on-one interaction and producing immediate response to input answers. Computer Aided Instruction allows users to demonstrate mastery and learn new material at their own pace.

More so, Oreta (2006) claimed that rapid development of computer technologies which include powerful and affordable microcomputers and reliable and user-friendly software has started to change the delivery of instruction in higher education. Computers have greatly increased the ability of students to perform calculations and to process large amount of data. As a result, the type and

nature of problems and mathematical techniques taught in school may have to be changed or modified so that the usefulness of the computer can be maximized in the teaching-learning process.

Furthermore, Caccam, et.al (2013) posited that since the start of rapid advances in technology, the need to integrate technological knowledge in education and industry has been recognized. In order to address this need, the concept of e-learning has been established. E-learning stands for ‘electronic learning,’ that is, associating the utilization of electronic materials to learning. Today, the term e-learning has captured a wider scope from the use of Personal Computers and the Internet to the utilization of more advanced applications, as well as devices or tools for more effective teaching and learning.

Cajilig (2009) on her study about Integration of Information and Communication Technology in Mathematics Teaching in Metro Manila Public Secondary Schools found out that Computer-aided teaching: Intel Teach to the Future, Text to teach, Micro lessons, Algebra through visual representations, Knowledge Networking (Korea) Using software enhanced understanding of math concepts.

Methodology

Research Design

The study made used of the descriptive survey research design. Andales (2008) defines the descriptive survey research design as a process which deals with the relationships between variables, the testing of the hypothesis and the development of generalizations, principles of theories that have universal validity.

In this study, the teaching of Mathematics with the use of computer aided materials was explored. It also described the effectiveness of this teaching approach, as perceived by the respondents to the study habits, class participation and problem-solving skills of the pupils. Furthermore, the study made use of the descriptive survey research design because the survey method was employed in gathering the data of this study. The researcher-made questionnaire was used.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were all the Grade six pupils of Quiterio San Jose Elementary School during the SY 2014 – 2015 where a total of 258 pupils answered the questionnaire.

Instrument

In conducting this study, the researcher used questionnaire consisting of two parts. Part I dealt on the documentary analysis about the respondents’ profile in terms of sex, age, monthly family income and parents’ educational attainment.

Part II dealt on the effectiveness of the computer aided materials in teaching mathematics with respect to study habits, class participation and problem-solving skills. There were ten items in each variable.

Procedure

The study was guided by a Gantt Chart of activities. Permission from concerned authorities in the Division of Rizal was secured by the researcher. When the permission was sought, the researcher administered the questionnaire-checklist to the grade six pupils of Quiterio San Jose Elementary School and waited for the results to be recorded one by one to facilitate the administration of the test and to avoid discrepancies in the testing. Equal treatment on administering the test was given. The researcher prepared a modified questionnaire-checklist that was validated by different experts. After the administration and retrieval of the questionnaire-checklist, data were treated utilizing the appropriate statistical tools. Analysis and interpretation of data ensued. Summary of findings, conclusions and recommendations followed.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

Profile of the Respondents

Table 1. *Profile of the Respondents*

	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Age			
11	69	26.7	3
12	106	41.1	1
13 and above	83	32.2	2
Total	258	100.0	
Sex			
Male	135	52.3	1
Female	123	47.7	2
Total	258	100.0	
Monthly Family Income			

20,000 and above	4	1.6	4
16, 000-19, 000	1	.4	5
11, 000-15, 999	24	9.3	3
5, 000-10, 999	190	73.6	1
4, 999 and below	39	15.1	2
Total	258	100.00	
Parents' Educational Attainment			
College Graduate	55	21.3	3
Vocational Graduate	25	9.7	4
High School Graduate	111	43.0	1
Elementary Graduate	67	26.0	2
Total	258	100.0	

As indicated, most of the respondents are aged 12 years old. Majority is male at 52.3%. The monthly family income signifies that almost three quarters of the respondents have income ranging from 5,000 to 10,999 pesos at 73.6%. The parents' educational attainment showed that 43.0% are high school graduate, 21.3% are college graduate, 26.0% are elementary graduate and 9.7% are vocational graduate.

Effectiveness of Computer-Aided Materials in Teaching Mathematics as Perceived by Pupil-respondents with Respect to Study Habits, Class Participation, and Problem-Solving Skills

Table 2. Perception of the Pupils on the Effectiveness of Computer Aided Materials in Teaching Mathematics with Respect to Study Habits

A	Description	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
<i>The use of computer aided materials in teaching Mathematics . . .</i>			
1.	encourages me to study harder.	4.67	Very Much Effective
2.	motivates me to enjoy the lesson.	4.62	Very Much Effective
3.	increases my span of attention in the class.	4.52	Very Much Effective
4.	encourages me to take extra effort to learn the lessons to be learned.	4.47	Much Effective
5.	captures my willingness and interest in the lesson.	4.47	Much Effective
6.	boosts my eagerness to learn concepts of the lesson.	4.38	Much Effective
7.	enhances my eagerness to explore other concepts.	4.48	Much Effective
8.	helps me develop my own study habits.	4.50	Very Much Effective
9.	provides creative lesson presentation that motivates me to improve my study habits.	4.47	Much Effective
10.	Encourages me to think independently.	4.62	Very Much Effective
Composite Mean		4.52	Very Much Effective

A review of the data in the table, it can be seen that the overall weighted mean is 4.52 interpreted as very much effective. Item 1 stating that the use of computer aided materials in teaching Mathematics encourages the pupils to study harder obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.67, while is item 6 stating that the use of computer aided materials in teaching Mathematics boosts their eagerness to learn concepts of the lesson ranked last with a weighted mean of 4.38 and has an interpretation of much effective.

The finding suggests that the use of computer aided materials in teaching Mathematics is very successful in providing the pupils with better study habits. Because study habits is the ways that a pupil study the habits that they have formed during school years.

According to Aliasgari, Riahinia and Mojdehavar (2010) concerning the effect of Computer Aided Materials on the attitudes and learning of students studying mathematics with a software program provided by the Department of Educational Technology that allowed students to direct their learning.

Table 3. Perception of the Pupils on the Effectiveness of Computer Aided Materials in Teaching Mathematics with Respect to Class Participation

B.	Description	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
<i>The use of computer aided materials in teaching Mathematics . . .</i>			
1.	enhances my participation in the classroom discussion.	4.50	Very Much Effective
2.	increases my participation in group activities.	4.45	Much Effective
3.	helps me cope to the day-to-day learning activities.	4.36	Much Effective
4.	helps me easily adjust to the lessons.	4.39	Much Effective
5.	overcomes shyness in participation in class discussion.	4.34	Much Effective
6.	develops my willingness to participate in group discussions.	4.24	Much Effective
7.	provides various activities to improve my class participation.	4.12	Much Effective
8.	helps me to share ideas regularly on various Mathematics lesson.	4.17	Much Effective
9.	enhances my willingness to take an active part during discussions.	4.24	Much Effective
10.	develops my interest in developing my classroom participation.	4.48	Much Effective
Composite Mean		4.33	Much Effective

In examination of the table, the overall weighted mean showed a result of 4.33 interpreted as much effective. Top in rank is item 1 stating that the use of computer aided materials in teaching Mathematics enhances my participation in the classroom discussion which obtained a weighted mean of 4.50 interpreted as very much effective, while lowest in rank is item 7 stating that the use of computer aided materials in teaching Mathematics provide various activities to improve my class participation which obtained a weighted mean of 4.12 interpreted as much effective. The result implies that computer aided materials in teaching Mathematics help the pupils to interact better in class.

Findings are congruent to the findings of Rodrigo (2008) where it was found that student survey reflected a strong preference among students for ICT based delivery at education. They believed that lessons were more fun and interesting when teachers used power point, educational videos or ICT based drills.

Table 4. Perception of the Pupils on the Effectiveness of Computer Aided Materials in Teaching Mathematics with Respect to Problem Solving Skills

C.	Description	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
<i>The use of computer aided materials in teaching Mathematics . . .</i>			
1.	provides exercises that encourage me to understand problem solving.	4.49	Much Effective
2.	lessens difficulty in coping with problem solving lessons.	4.37	Much Effective
3.	enhances my ability to transform worded problems to mathematical form.	4.55	Very Much Effective
4.	encourages me to solve problem solving with confidence .	4.42	Much Effective
5.	helps me better recognize the operation needed in the problem.	4.41	Much Effective
6.	is relevant and responsive in developing problem solving skills.	4.22	Much Effective
7.	Boosts computational skills in solving problem.	4.28	Much Effective
8.	helps me easily understand the problem solving.	4.33	Much Effective
9.	presents concepts and ideas to develop my problem solving skills.	4.21	Much Effective
10.	stimulates my desire to develop problem skills through varied examples.	4.45	Much Effective
Composite Mean		4.37	Much Effective

In perusing the table, the overall weighted mean showed a result of 4.37 interpreted as much effective which is also the interpretation of the given descriptions in the same table except for the top in rank which is interpreted as very much effective. Highest among them is item 3 indicating that the use of computer aided materials in teaching Mathematics enhances their ability to transform worded problems to mathematical form which gained a weighted mean of 4.55, while last from all the items is item 9 indicating that the use of computer aided materials in teaching Mathematics presents concepts and ideas to develop my problem solving skills which gained a weighted mean of 4.21. As the result implies, computer aided materials in teaching Mathematics greatly improve problem solving skills of pupils.

Findings are aligned with the findings of Huang (2012) indicates that the computer assisted mathematical problem-solving system in the form of a network instruction website can effectively as a tool for teachers engaged in remedial education.

Significant Difference on the Perception of the Respondents on the Effectiveness of Computer Aided Materials in Teaching Mathematics with Respect to the Different Aspects in Terms of Their Profile

Table 5. Result of the Test on the Significant Difference on the Perception of the Respondents on the Effectiveness of Computer Aided Materials in Teaching Mathematics in Terms of Their Profile

Aspect	F-value	p-value	Decision	Verbal Interpretation
Sex				
Study Habits	1.427	0.233	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Class Participation	8.464	0.004	Reject Ho	Significant
Problem Solving Skills	.006	0.937	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Age				
Study Habits	1.962	0.120	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Class Participation	2.012	0.113	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Problem Solving Skills	1.152	0.329	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Monthly family Income				
Study Habits	3.159	0.015	RejectHo	Significant
Class Participation	2.309	0.058	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Problem Solving Skills	0.246	0.912	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Parents Educational Attainment				
Study Habits	1.241	0.296	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Class Participation	0.384	0.765	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Problem Solving Skills	0.457	0.712	Accept Ho	Not Significant

It can be seen from the table that two p-value, 0.004 for class participation and 0.015 for study habits are lower than 0.05. This means that the test failed to reject the null hypothesis for class participation in terms of sex and study habits in terms of monthly family income. It is concluded that the perception of the male and female respondents on the effectiveness of computer aided instruction varies with

respect to class participation, likewise their perception with respect to effectiveness of computer aided instruction on the study habits differ when grouped by monthly family income.

For the rest of the variables, the result of the test showed p-values greater than the 0.05 level of significance. This means that the null hypothesis is accepted. The result implies that the perception of the respondents on the effectiveness of computer aided materials in teaching Mathematics with respect to study habits, class participation and problem skills is not affected by their age and parents' educational attainment.

As conducted in the study of Staples, Pugach and Himes (2005) that computer-based mathematics curriculum can be useful tool in the advancement towards students' academic gains.

Conclusions

The study concluded that there is no significant difference on the perception of the respondents on the effectiveness of computer aided materials in teaching Mathematics with respect to study habits, class participation and problem solving in terms of their age, monthly family income and parents' educational attainment. The perceptions of the male and female-respondents on the effectiveness of computer aided instruction varies with respect to class participation, likewise their perception with respect to effectiveness of computer aided instruction on the study habits differ when grouped by monthly family income.

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